

ROLE OF OLFACTOR LEXICON IN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

Burkhanova Mashkhurakhan Muhammadovna

Senior lecturer of Fergana State University,

Doctor of Philosophy in Philology (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7794706>

Abstract. This article focuses on smell and the linguistic means of its expression, which are studied in modern linguistics, and the author focuses on the importance of smell in today's linguistics, verbal and non-verbal means of expressing smell.

Keywords. Perception, cognitive linguistics, linguistic tools, verbal and non-verbal tools, olfactory, odoric lexicon, olfactory sign, olfactory lexicon, olfactory metaphor, olfactory image, lexemes representing smell, odor qualities.

A person receives information about the external world through five sense organs. These channels of information (smell, sight, hearing, touch, taste) form a general system of human perception of the world. Perception includes a wide range of events and processes, from a person's simple awareness of what is happening to him at one time or another, to the generalization of emotional experience in the form of reflection. It is a cognitive process that includes situations such as perception, interpretation, and conclusion, and the resulting images depend on each of these factors. Perception is formed as a result of a person's constant contact with the outside world. Information received through the sense of smell is also one of the methods of perception. In ancient times, this sense was of special importance for man, because it helped him to control the world. The sense of smell, which developed long before the senses of sight and hearing, ensured the existence of living organisms in nature. However, gradually these types of intuitions lost their importance. As a result, researchers became interested in the sense of smell. The linguist Ullmann considers smell and taste to be primitive, and hearing and sight to be higher senses [Ullmann 1951: 277]. Some researchers even believe that the semantic field of "smell" does not exist. D. Sperber writes about this: "... Smells have no semantic field. The concept of smell includes only general terms for subcategories such as "odor" and "aroma". (Sperber. 2000: 87)]. However, the results of modern research on olfactory, tactile, and taste senses and their role in the process of understanding the world prove that the importance of these senses has been underestimated. For this reason, in recent years, the interest of world linguists in "primitive" types of perception, including the field of smell, has increased significantly. Today, the sense of smell is becoming an object of research in various fields of science: biology, medicine, neurophysiology, linguistics and literature, chemistry and

physics, psychology, cultural studies and sociology. In linguistics, the traditional approach to the study of perception and individual sensations, especially olfactory sensations, is limited to their representation through lexical units. The main object of study in scientific research in the field of smell is the lexical-semantic category of smell. In order to define such lexical units, that is, concepts related to the olfactory direction, researchers use odorative vocabulary, olfactory vocabulary, olfactory cognition, olfactory process, olfactory image, olfactory vocabulary, olfactory symbol, olfactory lexicon, olfactory metaphor, offactor they use different terms such as image, olfactory lexemes, olfactory qualities.

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